

“LOCALISATION OF THE SDGs: GUIDELINES FOR POLICY-MAKERS ON INTRODUCING THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS TO THE LOCAL GOVERNANCE SCHEME”

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Abstract

Cities have a central role in the national, regional and eventually, global processes towards becoming more sustainable. The paper examines the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) since their appearance in 2015. Based on governance and process management principles, it introduces a tailored toolkit, which acts as a guide for policy stakeholders who aim to adopt the SDGs. The city’s identity, agenda and capacities are crucial for determining a decision’s outcome and consist the first step for efficient policy design. Behavioural change and education are inextricably linked to the transition towards the new era. Localising the SDGs should be seen as a dynamic process that evolves throughout time and adapts to new circumstances.

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1. Introduction

The world is constantly changing. Some needs remain the same while others appear less important in some geographical areas due to their different priorities. According to Brundtland's report:

*“Sustainable Development is the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”
(WCED, 1987).*

Based on the aforementioned, there are three main pillars of sustainability that represent the main aspects of human life on the planet. These are economic growth, environmental protection and social equality (WCED, 1987). All three are interrelated and interdependent. Thinking schematically, they could be placed on the vertices of a triangle. A change in one of them affects the other two sides. Of course, in reality the described system is much more complex than a simple theoretical approach. Still, this explanation provides a useful first insight on the interlinkage between human society, its activities and the environment (Antoniadi, 2018; 2020).

In year 2015, “the Heads of State and Government agreed to set the world on a path towards sustainable development through the adoption of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development¹. This global development agenda includes 17 Sustainable Development Goals (from now on SDGs), which set out quantitative objectives across the social, economic, and environmental dimensions of sustainable development” (UN SDSN, 2016). With the adoption of the SDGs, countries and cities faced challenges that led to one common question: “How do we operationalize these global goals?” (UN SDSN, 2016). The practical complexity significantly challenges everyone committed to meet the goals of the future.

This paper examines the Sustainable Development Goals under the spectrum of SDG 11 namely, Sustainable Cities and Communities. First, it briefly introduces the history of the 17 SDGs followed by a more detailed analysis of SDG-local applications. Moreover, it presents the United Nations Sustainable Development Solutions Network's (SDSN) attempts to localize the goals in order to adapt them to the needs and capabilities of local areas and cities. The research continues by focusing on the local governance and presents an approach for SDG-localization from the perspective of policy and procedure management. Based on governance and policy management principles, it introduces a general toolkit with directions for policymakers in pursuit of developing more efficient policies and procedures regarding the effective integration of the SDGs at the local level.

2. Literature Review

2.1. A brief history: from MDGs to SDGs

In year 2000 and after long negotiations and discussions, the United Nations member states agreed upon 8 Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) whose completion would lead to the eradication of severe issues around the world by 2015 (SDGE, no date; United Nations, 2015). The goals seemed to refer to all countries; in reality though, they were considered to be addressing problems that occur mainly in developing countries (United Nations, 2012). Eventually, the MDGs have been criticized as a vague set of wishes rather than a comprehensive toolkit. There were serious omissions such as human rights, economic development and gender equality while goals such as “ensuring environmental sustainability” remained unclear with regards to their context (Fehling, M. et al, 2013). All the aforementioned were about to change in 2015.

2.2. 2015 and onwards

That year, the countries agreed on a new package of goals called “Sustainable Development Goals” (SDGs). This set of 17 goals seems to be more concrete and addresses challenges worldwide regardless the countries’ level of development. 169 targets accompany them acting like specifiers of what is actually pursued by each goal. Year 2030 is the “new deadline”, the time all goals should have been met at a significant level (United Nations, no date). Moving to the present, it is interesting to examine what the SDG-impact is so far with regards to its presence at the local urban level.

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2.3. Measuring SDGs: what has been done so far? How does it work?

The indicators are complemented by national and regional indicators, which are closer to national and regional priorities. Hence, additional sets of indicators appear in different geographical areas in order to reach a more holistic insight into the country’s or region’s case. National statistical systems are responsible for compiling the data according to fundamental principles and then, share them at a national, regional and global level (SDG AcademyX, 2020). However, the SDSN mentioned serious challenges that need to be examined and taken into consideration in decision-making.

There are official indicators that lack agreed-upon methodologies or available official data. Some countries' national statistical offices lack the capacity to produce relevant data. There are questions around unofficial sources of data, such as big data or data produced by private tech companies, which provide huge opportunities for measuring crucial SDG indicators, but lack a role in the formal reporting system. Finally, there are important topics not covered in the official indicator framework –how, for instance, do we measure the "spillover" effect of one country's SDG action on another country's progress (SDG AcademyX, 2020)?

2.4. What happens at the local level?

SDSN realised that “when they produced the country level editions, these did not take into account differences that could exist within the country itself and across different cities.” (SDSN 2019 Report). It is important to understand the central role each city can play in the national, regional and eventually, global process towards becoming more sustainable. With over half of the global population (55.7%) residing in urban areas (The World Bank, 2018) and expecting it to increase to 68% by 2050 (United Nations, 2018), cities are called to take action. At this point, a main question arises: How do we operationalize the global goals? The following section examines ways for approaching the SDGs at the local level. Further, it develops a general toolkit for policymakers, which can serve as the baseline for adopting new governance schemes.

3. Process Management Tool for the SDGs

Introduction to the section

The section introduces a process management toolkit for policy stakeholders in relation to the SDGs. Based on governance and policy management principles and the multifaceted nature of the SDGs, it presents a series of steps that help decision-makers design the most suitable approach and gain a holistic insight on their city's potential. The steps are represented in graph 1 and unfold as follows below.

Graph 1: Steps for Localising the SDGs

1. Identity:

It is extremely essential to first define the main characteristics of the examining case as the latter will determine the process' following steps. These characteristics are related to the natural landscape (highland, lowland, seaside etc), natural resources (forest, river, mines etc), climate, locality type (urban, rural), economic activities (primary, secondary, tertiary production sector), social characteristics (population, average age of citizens, active number of citizens etc), main type of governance (top-down, bottom-up etc). It is also important to consider any cultural characteristics

that appear in the city as it may help the decision-makers introduce measures and initiatives closer to the citizens' identity.

Turning the focus to the SDGs, one could argue that based on the city's elements, the decision-makers can define a first set of goals that seem to be more relevant. As a second phase, the city's agenda could be linked to the targets – again based on a first glance –. Note that during the two phases described, no goal or target gets excluded; it just offers a first insight on what is more applicable and relevant to the city.

2. Define relevant targets & indicators:

In the second step, it is time to consider the city's capacities, such as time, personnel, financial resources etc. These will determine the city's ability to insert particular indicators and eventually, adapt others. The United Nations have identified 169 targets for 17 goals. In order to define which targets are demonstrable at the local level, the research used a mapping approach as explained below.

The selection is based on the perception regarding the targets' implementation. There are targets whose realization requires the involvement of national or even international authorities. The local actors may play a crucial role, but the decisions depend on a higher level of governance. Therefore, such targets are not included in the list. In order to recognize a target as *eligible*, it has to be demonstrable at a local level without the need for permission on behalf of higher governing bodies. Hence, a question arises:

Q: Is target A demonstrable at a local level without constraints by higher governing bodies due to dependency?

After collecting all the relevant targets and indicators, the paper examines their "level of connection" with respect to the main SDG-11 targets. It has to be noted, that at this step the focus moves from the target as such to its indicators in order to become more accurate. In other words, there might be targets which have been recognized as "eligible". However, each target has its own indicators but not all of them can be reached at a local level mainly due to lack of authorship or even resources. Thus, the arising questions are:

q1: Could the examining indicator be integrated at the local level?

This particular question could be either positive or negative. In the first case, the indicator is directly integrated. However, if the question receives a negative answer, a second one appears.

q2: Could the examining indicator be adapted at the local level?

It may be possible to scale down an indicator by adapting some of its features in order to apply it at the local level. However, it may be also possible to lack the necessary tools for data collection thus, even though the city may consider the examining information important, it will not be possible to apply that particular indicator. In such a case, it has been noted that cities can complement the existing indicators by inserting additional "to-the-point" ones.

After having completed the selection of the "eligible" targets and indicators –based on the answers to the previous questions–, policymakers will have a number of x targets and indicators they will be expected to meet. After examining every target and their indicators at the local level, the findings can be incorporated into one new table, which shows all the targets and indicators that could be reached -at least partly- by local and regional authorities. In other words, it would be helpful to re-organise the "eligible" ones by categorizing them in a way that helps decision-makers approach and design

relevant policies. Note that the results differ geographically and highly depend on both the city’s characteristics, its agenda and capacities.

Example given:

Keep each target under the relevant goal while recognizing the interconnection they have with targets assigned under a different goal.

Table 1: Eligible targets per goal at the local level

The list is indicative and should not be used as such without prior consideration of the specific characteristics a city may have.

Goal	Target
	1.4 By 2030, ensure that all men and women have... access to basic services
	3.6 By 2030, halve the number of deaths and injuries from road traffic accidents
	4.1 By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes
	4.3 By 2030, ensure equal access for all women and men to affordable and quality technical, vocational and tertiary education, including university
	6.1 By 2030, achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water
	6.b Support and strengthen the participation of local communities in improving water and sanitation management
	7.1 By 2030, ensure universal access to affordable, reliable and modern energy services
	7.2 By 2030, increase substantially the share of renewable energy in the energy mix
	11* *Since the paper focuses on urban areas, all targets of goal 11 are eligible.
	12.5 By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse
	12.6 Encourage companies to adopt sustainable practices and to integrate sustainability information into their reporting cycle
	13.1 Strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters

3. Prioritise:

Every city has its own characteristics and potential as well as needs. Hence, it is reasonable to have different policies and priorities depending on the local demands. It should be noted, that priorities change and adapt to new challenges throughout time. Therefore, it is important to regularly revise the city’s agenda and examine the level of urgency for each goal and target. Likewise, the indicators are not equally urgent everywhere and tend to dynamically change after a certain period of time. The decision-makers are asked to decide on the urgency as it would help understand the indicators’ results in the next steps. Defining and understanding the level of urgency should be based on the city’s identity, agenda and further, capacities. For no reason should the term be seen as a means to degrade or upgrade a particular goal, target or indicator. In an attempt to quantify the aforementioned the following table is recommended:

Score	Level of Urgency
1	Less Urgent
2	Urgent
3	Highly Urgent

4. Collect:

Finding and collecting data is a complicated process that requires time, agility and patience. However, it is necessary in order to understand the city’s status, recognize its needs and design proper policies. Collecting data will happen within a certain period of time and will continue after that period for the next one³. In the current paper, there are two columns stating the real and expected data. The “real” column indicates the moment the decision-makers have decided to examine the at-that-moment information. It could be defined on an annual basis but also on a shorter or longer period. The “expected” column shows the tendency for that particular indicator. For example, the goal for the unemployment rates would be to have a reduction. Thus, the tendency would show a reduction. ↓

On the opposite direction, a willingness to increase the percentage of green spaces would have a positive tendency. ↑ Sometimes, it can be possible to define the tendency in details in case the decision-makers have certain numerical goals in their agenda. Note though, that it is not necessary to include a number.

Table 3: Example of collected indicators and data

The table is formed based on one city’s identity and having considered its characteristics, the decision-makers’ agenda as well as the capacities.

The table below is indicative. It is highly recommended to avoid using it as such without prior consideration of its relevance to the city-case one would like to apply it or without following the previous steps described in this document. No scores are included.

Indicators		Score			Metric System	Urgency			Comments
		Real ₂₀₁₉	Expected	Real ₂₀₂₀		1	2	3	
AA									
a1	Proportion of population living in households with access to basic services (water, sanitation, electricity, heating)		↑						
b1	Proportion of population that has convenient access to public transport, by sex, age and persons with disabilities		↑						
b2	Death rate due to road traffic injuries		↓						
f1	Recycling rate, tons of material recycled		↑						
h2	Proportion of population completing mandatory school		↑						
i1	Coverage of protected areas in relation to marine areas		↑						
k9	Proportion of youth (aged 15–24 years) not in education, employment or training		↓						

5. Code:

As mentioned in the previous step, each indicator gives their own and distinct results, which have a particular meaning for what they represent. These results though, cannot be used altogether in the following steps; it is important to create a common basis and subsequently, avoid potential

misinterpretations. Therefore, the Codification phase acts as a transition from the different results to a series of numbers/words which can be studied under a common framework.

There are several ways for coding with the simplest of them being to calculate the percentages. Certainly, someone may use a different approach, which is permitted as long as the indicators are not misused, the results can be properly interpreted and there are no biases that could alienate the process. This paper will use the percentage approach in order to keep it less complicated.

At this point, policymakers have a first set of data along with their tendency, the city’s capacities and characteristics. Can we stop now? Certainly, once all data are collected, policymakers may decide to work on designing and adopting adaptation plans and policies however, it is wise to add two further steps in order to ensure a better insight regarding indicators and targets as groups.

Combined with other indicators under the same target, would eventually support the development of holistic approaches and plans. In addition, it would help identify the causes and factors affecting an examined situation, which would further lead to potentially improved decisions and measures.

6. Level 1:

After having similarly codified data, the indicators can be approached under the same functions.

Parameter:

Weighting based on urgency: there are often indicators that need to be prioritized over others due to decisions by the local authorities. For more information, see “Prioritise” section.

Target 11.1
By 2030, ensure access for all to adequate, safe and affordable housing and basic services and upgrade slums
$\frac{\text{SUM of (indicators' scores)} * (\text{level of urgency})}{\text{Number of indicators}} = \frac{(a_1 * i_1) + (a_2 * i_2) + (a_3 * i_3) + \dots + (a_v * i_v)}{x}$

7. Level 2:

Same procedure as in Level 1, this time for the goal. At this step, instead of inserting the indicators in the function, one has to insert the targets meaning that Level 1 should have been calculated first. The parameter remains the same as previously.

Parameter:

Weighting based on urgency: there are often indicators that need to be prioritized over others due to decisions by the local authorities.

Goal 11
Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable
$\frac{\text{SUM of targets' scores}}{\text{Number of targets}} = \frac{A + B + C + \dots + v}{y}$

8. Reflection & Design:

Reflecting can be both objective and subjective depending on the approach a decision-maker may follow. To begin, objectively one could judge the results “satisfying” or “negative” simply by comparing the numbers representing the facts to those representing the expectations. Such a comparison though, would lack a concrete and clear explanation on the results’ origins as well as factors that affected them. Hence, it is necessary to take into consideration elements such as:

- Implemented policies which may support some targets more than others
- Necessary funding
- Level of collaboration among stakeholders (in terms of communication, resources, discussion etc.)
- Time: the moment of calculation plays a decisive role because every indicator and every target cannot be simultaneously implemented at the same level of success. For example, the number of tons of material recycled every year would need less time to be calculated than that of soil erosion in a city.

9. Arrows:

The arrows stand for repetition. Performance measurement is an iterative process, which supports the dynamic lifespan of a policy, project or activity at a local and regional level. It is important to note that the results might differ in every single stage of a process, mainly due to the factors of time and decision-making. After a certain period of time, decision-makers should keep in mind to re-consider the indicators they are using in order to make sure that most of the aspects of their policy are properly examined. It is possible that there will be no changes in the indicators list and that is of course, acceptable. It is also good to stay informed about the city's characteristics, hence, the city's identity as well as its capacities and agenda. In case of significant changes, it is necessary to re-define the next steps; otherwise, the scheme will be trapped in a vicious cycle based on non-applicable-to reality data.

Graph 1: Iterative cycle for Localising the SDGs

4. Discussion

The SDGs have been framed in such a way that cover most of –if not all– the human activities and also touch upon environmental and diplomatic issues. The initial arising questions would be how to approach the SDGs and how to operationalise the global goals? The idea would be to adopt the act local-think global concept. This type of bottom-up approach at the governance level (national, sub-national, local) helps accelerate local developments in an active and more engaging manner. A strict top-down centrally controlling scheme tends to get overloaded by the needs of each region and city and even though, it is necessary nation-wise, it's also imperative to be supplemented and facilitated by semi-autonomous local initiatives. Thus, subnational and local authorities are called to develop policies and vulnerability assessment reports (sensitivity, exposure, adaptive capacity, vulnerability) for their designated areas in order to ensure resilience and incorporate SDG aspects. What every stakeholder should keep in mind and carefully consider is how to scale-down the global goals without limiting their potential?

The prior is greatly challenging to be implemented however, not unattainable. Not all targets apply at the local level and not all targets apply at urban areas with different characteristics. One has to first examine the local identity and carefully define which indices can be incorporated. Such a process needs to be carefully conducted by policy-makers who shall also consider the aims, needs and capacities of their city. It is reasonable to have different policies and priorities depending on the local demands. It should be noted, that priorities change and adapt to new challenges throughout time. Therefore, it is important to regularly revise the city's agenda and examine the level of urgency for each goal (Antoniadi, 2019). Let's keep in mind that focusing on the local level requires expanding networking links in-and-out of the examining geographical borders. In other words, policy-makers are called to regularly communicate with fellow policy-makers from neighbouring or further-located urban centres, in order to learn from each other and provide support and expertise. Collaboration with various stakeholders, open exchange of ideas and knowledge, and active partnerships are necessary to build a solid basis for moving forward.

It is important to keep in mind that localising the SDGs can be an external and internal process. In other words, policymakers are called not only to adopt the SDGs in their city as a whole, but also integrate these goals into the municipality's structure and function. How else would the Municipality become a city leader without adapting its internal operations?

Behavioural change is inextricably linked to the transition towards the new era. Spreading awareness would be the very first step of a long and relatively slow-moving process. Redesigned education and introduction of appealing and –preferably– engaging motives and tools both at an individual and organisational level are fundamental for adapting lifestyles and changing mindsets.

Localising the SDGs should be seen as a dynamic process that evolves throughout time and adapts to new circumstances. There is a high need for consistent planning and management of sustainable policies and procedures. The city's unique identity along with its agenda and capacities are pivotal for effective decision-making. The goals, targets and indicators are dynamic and highly linked to each city. Hence, they may be different between urban areas. Even in the rare occasion of having two cities adopting the exact same goals and targets, the indicators may differ due to the cities' capacities, data needs and nature. Time is also crucial and may affect decisions on goals, targets and indicators as well as the level of urgency for every action. Therefore it is extremely important to monitor the process and repeat by moving back to the initial steps, those of defining goals and examining the city's elements, agenda and capacities.

5. Conclusion

Cities have a central role in the national, regional and eventually, global processes towards becoming more sustainable as 80% of the SDG targets contain an urban component (UN Habitat, no date; 2020). However, such transitions are quite complicated especially when they affect business-as-usual procedures and call for behavioural change. The paper introduces a practical toolkit based on policy and procedure management concepts and aims to facilitate the process of localizing the SDGs in local areas. Given the uniqueness of each city, there is still a high need for research and it is crucial to examine real case studies in order to gain a better insight on the challenges and opportunities that emerge before and during the localization process. Case studies will enrich theoretical approaches and they will also encourage the emergence of aspects that did not occur in theory.

Decisions and policies are dynamic processes that need to be assessed in every step of their progress in order to achieve positive results. It is essential to monitor and follow every single step from the design, to the implementation and finally, evaluation and monitor of a decision/policy. Such an approach would provide all the necessary data, which would serve as a “black box” to the particular process –thus, a major help for identifying any related factors and circumstances– but also as a guidance for any future decisions/policies –what lessons can be derived–.

Localising the SDGs will contribute to the city’s balanced, resilient and sustainable transition. And the latter can be successfully achieved through policies designed and implemented by a healthy and dynamic governance scheme.

We need to work together and leave no-one behind, in order to ensure what is called a decent balance on the planet. There is still a long way ahead. Developments of such an extent cannot happen in one day, especially when they require behavioural change. However, it takes only a moment to decide on adopting a different mindset. What is necessary, would be to have a clear and concrete plan (action plan), accompanied by entities’ dedication and willingness to move forward.

Notes

1. For more information, visit <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015/transformingourworld>.
2. The global indicator framework includes 231 unique indicators. Note that the total number of indicators listed in the global indicator framework of SDG indicators is 247. However, **twelve indicators** repeat under two or three different targets. For more information, <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/indicators-list/>
3. Since the process is dynamic in its whole, the same applies to its parts and smaller steps. Hence, data collection should not stop; rather data information should be examined after a certain time-period previously defined by the decision-makers. This way, it will be more efficient to examine the progress and move towards the next steps, those of implementing decisions, having a real-life practical impact and analyse all the relevant results.

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